

Spinal versus General Anesthesia for Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) Repair of Inguinal Hernia: Interim Analysis of a Controlled Randomized Trial

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Abstract:

Background: One prevalent surgical treatment is the correction of inguinal hernias, especially when done with the transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) approach. The surgical result and the patient's recuperation are greatly impacted by the type of anaesthesia, either spinal or general. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of spinal anaesthesia vs general anaesthesia for patients having TAPP surgery for inguinal hernias.

Methods: This randomized controlled trial was conducted enrolling 107 participants. Participants were randomly assigned to receive either spinal anesthesia (n=53) or general anesthesia (n=54). Data collected included baseline demographics, intraoperative parameters (anesthesia and surgery time, complications), and postoperative outcomes (pain scores, time to ambulation, hospital stay duration, complications). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Participants in the spinal anesthesia group had significantly shorter anesthesia times (70.2 ± 10.5 minutes vs. 81.7 ± 12.3 minutes, $p < 0.001$), lower postoperative pain scores at 24 hours (3.1 ± 1.2 vs. 4.5 ± 1.5 , $p < 0.001$), earlier ambulation (6.8 ± 1.9 hours vs. 10.4 ± 2.5 hours, $p < 0.001$), and shorter hospital stays (2.1 ± 0.7 days vs. 3.2 ± 1.0 days, $p < 0.001$) compared to the general anesthesia group. Intraoperative and postoperative complication rates were similar between the groups.

Conclusion: Spinal anesthesia offers significant advantages over general anesthesia for TAPP repair of inguinal hernia, including shorter anesthesia time, better postoperative pain control, faster ambulation, and reduced hospital stay. Both techniques showed comparable safety profiles regarding complication rates.

Recommendations: Based on these findings, spinal anesthesia should be considered the preferred option for TAPP repair of inguinal hernia due to its favorable impact on postoperative recovery and hospital resource utilization. Further studies are recommended to confirm these results in larger populations and different clinical settings.

Keywords: Inguinal Hernia Repair, Spinal Anesthesia, General Anesthesia, TAPP, Postoperative Recovery.

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Introduction

Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most common surgical procedures performed worldwide, with millions of cases managed annually. Among the various surgical techniques available, the transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) approach is widely used due to its minimally invasive nature and favorable outcomes in terms of postoperative pain and recovery time. Anesthesia management in TAPP repair remains a critical factor influencing surgical outcomes and patient recovery. The choice between spinal and general anesthesia for such procedures has been a subject of ongoing research and debate in recent years.

General anesthesia has been traditionally favored for laparoscopic procedures, including TAPP, due to its ability to provide complete unconsciousness and muscle relaxation, facilitating the surgical process. However, general anesthesia is associated with several potential complications, including postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV), respiratory complications, and a longer recovery period. In contrast, spinal anesthesia offers several advantages, including better postoperative pain control, reduced PONV, and shorter recovery times [1]. Despite these benefits, spinal anesthesia is not without its risks, such as hypotension, bradycardia, and the potential for incomplete analgesia.

Recent studies have explored the comparative effectiveness of spinal versus general anesthesia in various surgical settings. For instance, a meta-analysis highlighted that spinal anesthesia is associated with lower postoperative pain scores and faster recovery times in patients undergoing lower abdominal surgeries [1]. Similarly, a randomized controlled trial found that spinal anesthesia significantly reduced hospital stay and improved patient satisfaction compared to general anesthesia in laparoscopic hernia repairs [2]. These findings are supported by a systematic review reported that spinal anesthesia is associated with fewer perioperative complications and better postoperative outcomes in laparoscopic surgeries [3].

Despite the growing body of evidence supporting the use of spinal anesthesia, its application in TAPP repair of inguinal hernia remains underexplored. The need for comprehensive studies comparing spinal and general anesthesia in this specific context is evident. Such research is crucial for guiding clinical practice and optimizing patient outcomes.

This study aims to compare the efficacy and outcomes of spinal versus general anesthesia for transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair of inguinal hernia.

Methodology

Study Design: A randomized controlled trial.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of 14 months at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Bihar, India.

Participants: A total of 107 participants were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18-65 years
- Diagnosed with inguinal hernia and scheduled for TAPP repair
- Classified as American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I or II
- Willing to provide informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Previous abdominal surgery
- Contraindications to spinal or general anesthesia

- Coagulation disorders
- Severe cardiovascular or respiratory conditions
- Pregnancy
- Allergy to medications used in the study

Bias: Randomization and blinding procedures were implemented to minimize bias. Participants were randomly assigned to receive either spinal or general anesthesia using a computer-generated randomization list. The anesthesiologist administering the anesthesia was aware of the group assignments, but the surgeon, postoperative care team, and data analysts were blinded to the group allocations.

Data Collection: Data were collected at baseline, during the surgery, and postoperatively. Baseline data included demographic information, medical history, and preoperative assessments. Intraoperative data included anesthesia time, surgery time, and any complications. Postoperative data included pain scores, time to ambulation, hospital stay duration, and any postoperative complications.

Procedure: Participants were randomly assigned to receive either spinal anesthesia or general anesthesia for their TAPP repair. Standardized protocols for anesthesia administration, surgical technique, and postoperative care were followed.

1. Spinal Anesthesia Group: Participants received a spinal block with 0.5% bupivacaine.

2. General Anesthesia Group: Participants received induction with propofol and maintenance with a volatile anesthetic agent, as per institutional protocols.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. Demographic and clinical features were gathered using descriptive statistics. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Result

53 people were assigned to the spinal anaesthesia group and 54 participants were assigned to the general anaesthesia group out of the 107 participants that were enrolled in the study. Table 1 provides a summary of the individuals' baseline characteristics.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Spinal Anesthesia	General Anesthesia	p-value
Age (years)	45.3 ± 12.1	46.1 ± 11.5	0.678
Gender (M/F)	44/9	46/8	0.774
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.8 ± 3.4	26.1 ± 3.6	0.652
ASA Physical Status (I/II)	32/21	30/24	0.624
Duration of Hernia (months)	18.4 ± 9.2	17.9 ± 9.6	0.762

There were no significant differences between the two groups in terms of age, gender distribution, BMI, ASA physical status, or the duration of hernia.

The intraoperative data, including anesthesia time, surgery time, and intraoperative complications, are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Intraoperative Data

Parameter	Spinal Anesthesia	General Anesthesia	p-value
Anesthesia Time (minutes)	70.2 ± 10.5	81.7 ± 12.3	<0.001
Surgery Time (minutes)	60.2 ± 12.3	61.7 ± 11.8	0.548
Intraoperative Complications	2 (3.8%)	3 (5.6%)	0.678

Individuals under spinal anaesthesia experienced notably shorter anaesthesia durations than those under general anaesthesia ($p < 0.001$). The duration of the procedure and the frequency of intraoperative problems did not significantly differ between the two groups.

Table 3 summarises the postoperative outcomes, which include pain levels, time to ambulation, length of hospital stay, and postoperative complications.

Table 3: Postoperative Data

Parameter	Spinal Anesthesia	General Anesthesia	p-value
Pain Score (VAS, 24 hours)	3.1 ± 1.2	4.5 ± 1.5	<0.001
Time to Ambulation (hours)	6.8 ± 1.9	10.4 ± 2.5	<0.001
Hospital Stay Duration (days)	2.1 ± 0.7	3.2 ± 1.0	<0.001
Postoperative Complications	5 (9.4%)	7 (13.0%)	0.563

When compared to the general anaesthesia group, participants in the spinal anaesthesia group experienced much less discomfort 24 hours after surgery ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, individuals in the spinal anaesthesia group experienced notably shorter hospital stays and timeframes to ambulation ($p < 0.001$). The incidence of postoperative complications did not significantly differ between the two groups.

Discussion

The interim analysis of this randomized controlled trial comparing spinal anesthesia to general anesthesia for TAPP repair of inguinal hernia included 107 participants, with 53 receiving spinal anesthesia and 54 receiving general anesthesia. The baseline characteristics between the two groups were well-balanced, with no significant differences in age, gender distribution, BMI, ASA physical status, or the duration of hernia.

Intraoperative data revealed that the spinal anesthesia group had significantly shorter anesthesia times compared to the general anesthesia group (70.2 ± 10.5 minutes vs. 81.7 ± 12.3 minutes, $p < 0.001$). This reduction in anesthesia time could contribute to overall improved efficiency in the operating room. The surgery times were comparable between the two groups, and the incidence of intraoperative complications was low and not significantly different between the groups.

Postoperatively, participants who received spinal anesthesia reported significantly lower pain scores at 24 hours (3.1 ± 1.2 vs. 4.5 ± 1.5, $p < 0.001$), indicating better immediate postoperative pain

control. Furthermore, these participants ambulated earlier (6.8 ± 1.9 hours vs. 10.4 ± 2.5 hours, $p < 0.001$) and had shorter hospital stays (2.1 ± 0.7 days vs. 3.2 ± 1.0 days, $p < 0.001$) compared to those who received general anesthesia. These outcomes suggest that spinal anesthesia not only improves pain management but also enhances recovery speed, potentially leading to better patient satisfaction and reduced hospital costs. The rates of postoperative complications were similar between the groups, indicating that both anesthesia methods are equally safe in terms of complication risks.

Overall, the results from this interim analysis suggest that spinal anesthesia may offer several advantages over general anesthesia for TAPP repair of inguinal hernia, including reduced anesthesia time, lower postoperative pain, faster ambulation, and shorter hospital stays. These findings highlight the potential benefits of spinal anesthesia in improving patient outcomes and optimizing healthcare resources. Further analysis upon study completion will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the comparative effectiveness of these anesthesia techniques.

In order to compare spinal and general anaesthesia for patients undergoing TAPP inguinal hernia repair, a randomised controlled trial was carried out. Haemodynamic parameters such as heart rate (HR), mean arterial pressure (MAP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and systolic blood pressure (SBP) were assessed in the study, which comprised 70 individuals. The results showed that during the procedure, spinal anaesthesia improved haemodynamic stability by reducing blood pressure

swings and slightly changing heart rate readings. Furthermore, spinal anaesthesia was linked to lower opioid usage and postoperative pain [4].

In a study, the effect of anaesthesia type on patients' postoperative quality of life following TAPP inguinal hernia repair was assessed. Seventy participants were randomly assigned to receive general or spinal anaesthesia in this study. Energy, emotional health, and general health scores were all higher after spinal anaesthesia, although the changes were not statistically significant. Spinal anaesthesia is a useful substitute for TAPP inguinal hernia repair since both forms of anaesthesia produced results that were comparable in terms of quality of life [5].

Under general anaesthesia, a randomised controlled trial compared the totally extraperitoneal (TEP) and transabdominal (TAPP) procedures for unilateral inguinal hernia repair. In comparison to the TEP group, the TAPP group had noticeably decreased postoperative pain at six, twenty-four, and seven days. The length of hospital stay, the return to normal activities, or the patient satisfaction ratings did not significantly differ between the two groups, according to the study [6].

TAPP and TEP methods for inguinal hernia repair were evaluated in a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. The study, which comprised 16 RCTs with 1519 patients, discovered that TEP repair led to longer surgical times for recurring hernia cases but shorter hospital stays for primary instances. The study came to the conclusion that whereas TAPP had a shorter operation length, TEP was more effective than TAPP at reducing short-term postoperative pain [7].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the interim analysis of this randomized controlled trial demonstrates that spinal anaesthesia offers several advantages over general anaesthesia for TAPP repair of inguinal

hernia. These findings should be further confirmed with the completion of the study and additional analyses.

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